

Impact and Optimum Placement of Off-Shore Energy Generating Platforms

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Abstract

Understanding the influence of wave distribution, hydrodynamics and sediment transport is crucial for the placement of off-shore energy generating platforms. The TELEMAC suite is used for this purpose, and the performance of the triple coupling between TOMAWAC for wave propagation, TELEMAC-3D for hydrodynamics and SISYPHE for sediment transport is investigated for several mesh sizes, the largest grid having over 10 million elements. The coupling has been tested up to 3,072 processors and good performance is in general observed.

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1. Introduction

With the UK being surrounded by seas and facing very frequent and strong winds, one of the main source of renewable energy comes from the sea in the form of marine and off-shore wind turbine farms. The effect of the location of these farms on the current and sediment distribution is not very well known, however HPC might help study them more in depth.

This project aims at preparing the hydrodynamic TELEMAC suite [1] [2] for large scale simulations, involving wave propagation, three-dimensional hydrodynamics and sediment transport distribution. It is an energy-related project focusing on the preparation of the coupling of several modules of the TELEMAC suite, in order to have it ready to study the impact and optimum placement of off-shore energy generating platforms and to simulate the placement of marine turbines in coastal waters. The performance of the triple coupling will be carried out for very fine meshes for hydrodynamicists. This has not been done before but is necessary to understand local (0.1-1 m scale) and distant (1-10 km) impact. The project also has an ecological and environmental effect as performing large-scale calculations is required to assess the near and long-term impact of off-shore wind/marine turbine farms on local and distant coastal waters, especially in terms of sediment morphology.

Three modules of the TELEMAC suite are used, namely TOMAWAC (wave propagation), TELEMAC-3D (3-D hydrodynamics) and SISYPHE (sediment transport). They have recently been coupled, but the triple coupling has never been tested on a large number of processors and certainly not for large meshes (over 10 million 2-D elements). Note that TOMAWAC was not running in parallel at the beginning of the project, but that the newly released version v6p3r2 has got a parallel version of TOMAWAC. This version is used in this work.

All the physical modules of the TELEMAC suite are linked to the BIEF library, which is TELEMAC's internal library for finite elements and simple operations, and other libraries such as the one dealing with the MPI parallel implementation. Here is a quick overview of the TOMAWAC, TELEMAC-3D and SISYPHE modules:

- TOMAWAC: It is used to model wave propagation in coastal areas. A simplified equation for the spectro-angular density of wave action is solved for steady-state conditions, i.e. using a fixed water depth throughout the whole simulation.
- TELEMAC-3D: It allows to compute the hydrodynamics. The model was written primarily to solve the shallow water equations in 3-D format but it is now possible to solve the governing equations including dynamic pressure to allow shorter waves than those in a shallow water context (where wavelengths are required to be at least twenty times the water depth). This non-hydrostatic model formulation may also be important when modelling flows over trenches or on steep slopes.

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- **SISYPHE**: It is the state of the art sediment transport and bed evolution module of the TELEMAC suite. It can be used to model complex morphodynamics processes in various environments, such as coastal, rivers, lakes and estuaries, for different flow rates, sediment size classes and sediment transport modes.

The triple coupling is internal, with TELEMAC-3D calling TOMAWAC and SISYPHE as any other sub-routine. Each of the modules deals with its own mesh and set of boundary conditions.

2. Scientific case

The flow in the Liverpool Bay (see 1) is used as a support of this work. Liverpool Bay is located in the Eastern Irish Sea and has been selected as a test bed for the large scale morphological modelling. There are three off-shore wind farms within Liverpool Bay; Burbo Bank, North Hoyle and Rhyl Flats, consisting of 25, 30 and 25 monopile turbines respectively, with a monopile diameter of 4-5m. Liverpool Bay has complex hydrodynamics with density currents due to freshwater inflow of the Mersey and Dee estuaries. The open source code TELEMAC system has been used for the simulations, with TELEMAC-3D, together with the wave module TOMAWAC, and the sediment transport module SISYPHE. For 3-D modelling the original mesh is divided into 10 horizontal layers (each of them has got 5,776 nodes and 10,209 elements) to cover the water depth range, and hydrodynamics is solved by the Navier-Stokes Equations. Sediment grain size is spatially mapped using grain size classes.

Fig. 1. (a) Liverpool Bay bathymetry. The highlighted part shows the location of one of the off-shore wind farms (Rhyl Flats). (b) Zoom on the distribution of the wind farm.

Table 1. Grid size of the various meshes

	0 th Level	1 st Level	2 nd Level	3 rd Level	4 th Level	5 th Level
Nodes	5,776	21,765	84,370	332,088	1,317,556	5,248,620
Elements	10,209	40,836	163,344	653,376	2,613,504	10,454,016
Time (s)	-	0.46	1.67	6.43	26.14	122.26
Largest Edge (m)	10,955	5,477	2,738	1,369	685	342
Smallest Edge (m)	2.28	1.14	0.57	0.28	0.14	0.07

3. Mesh multiplication

Instead of generating large meshes from scratch, another approach is used, based on mesh multiplication (MM). Mesh multiplication (also known as global mesh refinement) is the process of uniformly refining all the elements, in the case of the TELEMAC suite, by splitting all the triangles of the 2-D bottom mesh into 4 sub-triangles. Several MM strategies already exist, and some of them have been developed for large parallel simulations within the various PRACE [3] [4] projects, but the current tool is serial as it is meant to be used by TELEMAC community which deals at most with a couple of millions of elements at most.

The algorithm works as follows:

- The input TELEMAC files are read in the TELEMAC native SELAFIN format (T3DGEO and T3DCLI). This format supports single precision.
- The new nodes are created, i.e. the centre of the edges and the centre of each original triangle.
- Each triangle is split into 4 sub-elements. The total number of elements corresponds to the final one, but the total number of nodes is over-estimated. Note that the edge centres are clearly identified as an edge centre of an internal element is counted twice, whereas an edge centre of a boundary element is counted only once.

- All the nodes are sorted, using their geometric coordinates, and the ones occurring twice correspond to the centres of the edges of the internal faces.
- The previous list is compressed to get rid of the nodes counted twice.
- The boundary condition type (inlet, outlet, liquid boundary,...) is allocated to the newly created nodes.
- The bathymetry is linearly interpolated to the new nodes.
- The mesh and boundary condition files are saved in double precision (format SELAFIND).

This algorithm does not work if a triangle has got two nodes belonging to 2 different boundaries, which might occur if only 1 triangle is used to mesh the end of a river. Such triangles have first to be split into 3 subtriangles built from 3 original nodes and the centre of the triangle, before MM is applied. This was what had to be done before using the Liverpool Bay mesh.

The timing to generate all the meshes, as well as their size are presented at the 4th line of Table 1 and about 2 minutes only are required to generate the 5th Level mesh containing about 10 million elements, on an old 4 processor desktop.

4. Highlights on work completed

The TELEMAC suite was ported onto Marenostrom (Bull) and ARCHER (Cray XC30) using the INTEL compiler on both machines. A good part of the work consisted of testing first TOMAWAC's performance in parallel, before focusing on the triple coupling.

An issue was raised in SISYPHE, in the BEDLOAD_DIFFIN subroutine, which is where the boundary conditions are set. The case where an element has only one node as a physical boundary but where the edge containing this node is an interface node was not taken into account. This is now fixed.

The TELEMAC suite allows serial preprocessing (using a tool call PARTEL) or parallel (using tools called PARTEL_PRELIM and PARTEL_PARA). Serial preprocessing was used up to LEVEL 4, but parallel preprocessing was required for LEVEL 5. The parallel preprocessing stage did not support double precision input before this project. This has been implemented in PARTEL_PRELIM and PARTEL_PARA. Table 2 shows the timing to generate the partitioned input files for TOMAWAC and it takes about 1 hour for 512, 1,024 and 2,048 sub-domains, mainly for I/Os issues.

Table 2. Preprocessing - TOMAWAC: 5th Level

Cores	Time (s)
512	3,545
1,024	3,550
2,048	3,683

5. Current performance

5.1. TOMAWAC

The performance of TOMAWAC is tested on Marenostrom. Results are only presented for LEVEL 2 to LEVEL 5, as we are interested by the performance for the largest simulations. Tables 3-6 show that good speed-up and efficiency are in general observed, especially for LEVEL 5.

Table 3. TOMAWAC: 2ndLevel - 3,600 time-steps - 12.42 per time-step

Cores	Time (s)	Speed-up	Efficiency (%)
64	179	1.00	100
128	82	2.18	109
256	81	2.21	55

Table 4. TOMAWAC: 3rdLevel - 3,600 time-steps - 12.42 per time-step

Cores	Time (s)	Speed-up	Efficiency (%)
128	732	1.00	100
256	245	2.98	149
512	178	4.11	102
1,024	188	3.89	49

Table 5. TOMAWAC: 4thLevel - 7,200 time-steps - 6.21 per time-step

Cores	Time (s)	Speed-up	Efficiency (%)
128	6,723	1.00	100
256	3,581	1.88	94
512	2,020	3.32	83
1,024	1,137	5.91	74
2,048	1,106	6.07	38

Table 6. TOMAWAC: 5th Level - 7,200 time-steps - 6.21 per time-step

Cores	Time (s)	Speed-up	Efficiency (%)
512	8,671	1.00	100
1,024	2,936	2.95	147
2,048	2,076	4.17	104

5.2. TOMAWAC - TELEMAC-3D - SISYPHE

The triple coupling is now investigated on ARCHER. As for the previous simulations, the preprocessing is serial up to LEVEL 4 and parallel for LEVEL 5. Decent speed-up is observed for most of the meshes and simulations, apart maybe when going from 768 to 3,072 cores for LEVEL 5 (see Tables 7-10).

Table 7. triple coupling: 2ndLevel - 3,600 time-steps

Cores	Time (s)	Speed-up	Efficiency (%)
96	769	1.00	100
192	597	1.29	64
384	356	2.16	54

Table 8. triple coupling: 3rdLevel - 1,200 time-steps

Cores	Time (s)	Speed-up	Efficiency (%)
192	635	1.00	100
384	343	1.85	93
768	232	2.73	68

Table 9. triple coupling: 4thLevel - 1,200 time-steps

Cores	Time (s)	Speed-up	Efficiency (%)
384	970	1.00	100
768	575	1.69	84
1,536	325	2.98	75

Table 10. triple coupling: 5th Level - 1,200 time-steps

Cores	Time (s)	Speed-up	Efficiency (%)
768	1,819	1.00	100
1,536	1,144	1.59	78
3,072	1,139	1.60	40

The performance analysis tool CRAYPAT is run for LEVEL 5 (768, 1,536 and 3,072 cores) to try to identify why there is no speed-up going from 1,536 to 3,072 cores. For less than 768 cores, most time is spent in the method of characteristics stage (streamline*), but from 1,536 on, time is mainly spent in the MPI collectives, with MPI_ALLTOALLV, used in the method of characteristics again, becoming very costly for the 3,072 core case.

Samp%	Samp	Imb. Samp	Imb. Samp%	Group Function
100.0%	221619.3	--	--	Total

52.4%	116081.7	--	--	USER

13.1%	29096.2	19617.8	40.3%	streamline_mp_schar41_per_4d_
7.9%	17513.8	1553.2	8.2%	semimp_
6.9%	15217.9	2142.1	12.4%	qbrek1_
4.2%	9221.1	1929.9	17.3%	totnrj_
2.3%	5206.0	455.0	8.0%	vc13pp_
2.2%	4798.1	807.9	14.4%	assve1_
1.9%	4300.7	467.3	9.8%	gtsh41_
1.7%	3758.3	522.7	12.2%	streamline_mp_bief_interp_
1.7%	3745.8	352.2	8.6%	conw4d_
1.5%	3337.4	1952.6	37.0%	mt02pp_
1.1%	2337.9	429.1	15.5%	ov_
=====				
41.5%	92080.3	--	--	MPI

28.2%	62587.3	17369.7	21.8%	MPI_ALLREDUCE
10.2%	22602.6	7091.4	23.9%	mpi_waitall
2.0%	4404.1	1539.9	25.9%	mpi_alltoallv
=====				
6.1%	13436.3	--	--	ETC

4.6%	10246.2	976.8	8.7%	__intel_memset
1.0%	2222.5	473.5	17.6%	__intel_ssse3_rep_memcpy
=====				

Samp%	Samp	Imb. Samp	Imb. Samp%	Group Function
100.0%	136450.8	--	--	Total

54.6%	74466.7	--	--	MPI

33.5%	45655.8	12929.2	22.1%	MPI_ALLREDUCE
9.0%	12329.8	2721.2	18.1%	mpi_alltoallv
7.9%	10777.0	4689.0	30.3%	mpi_waitall
3.5%	4829.3	373.7	7.2%	mpi_alltoall
=====				
40.6%	55382.8	--	--	USER

9.6%	13154.9	10287.1	43.9%	streamline_mp_schar41_per_4d_
6.4%	8759.8	583.2	6.2%	semimp_
5.5%	7546.3	1069.7	12.4%	qbrek1_
3.7%	4995.0	767.0	13.3%	totnrj_
1.8%	2465.3	326.7	11.7%	assve1_
1.7%	2339.5	240.5	9.3%	vc13pp_
1.3%	1835.1	462.9	20.2%	gtsh41_
1.3%	1728.5	304.5	15.0%	streamline_mp_bief_interp_
1.1%	1497.3	1354.7	47.5%	mt02pp_
=====				
4.8%	6590.2	--	--	ETC

3.7%	5041.3	619.7	11.0%	__intel_memset
=====				

```

===== Observations and suggestions =====
Samp% | Samp | Imb. | Imb. | Group
      |      | Samp | Samp% | Function
      |      |      |      | PE=HIDE

100.0% | 123625.0 | -- | -- | Total
-----
| 77.2% | 95382.2 | -- | -- | MPI
-----
|| 33.8% | 41807.2 | 4172.8 | 9.1% | mpi_alltoallv
|| 30.5% | 37732.1 | 10724.9 | 22.1% | MPI_ALLREDUCE
|| 7.2% | 8914.9 | 4826.1 | 35.1% | mpi_waitall
|| 5.1% | 6283.3 | 352.7 | 5.3% | mpi_alltoall
-----
| 20.4% | 25176.2 | -- | -- | USER
-----
|| 5.5% | 6789.7 | 5684.3 | 45.6% | streamline_mp_schar41_per_4d_
|| 3.3% | 4061.4 | 641.6 | 13.6% | semimp_
|| 2.9% | 3580.2 | 551.8 | 13.4% | qbrek1_
|| 1.9% | 2380.2 | 408.8 | 14.7% | totnrj_
-----
| 2.5% | 3060.1 | -- | -- | ETC
-----
| 1.8% | 2216.4 | 395.6 | 15.2% | __intel_memset
=====

===== Observations and suggestions =====

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6. Summary

Testing the triple coupling between TOMAWAC-TELEMAC-3D-SISYPHE has been performed at scale for a 10 million element grid on up to 3,072 cores. Good speed-up is usually observed, but MPI_ALLTOALLV collective seems to hinder better performance.

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